

DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS OF THE GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION SYSTEM

Shonazarov Asror Makhmaisoyevich

SamDU, Doctor of philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7424124>

Abstract. *The scientific article envisages a comprehensive development of communication culture and socio-psychological professional competence of school principals in the management process on the basis of modern approaches.*

Keywords: *general education, school, management, socio-psychological, competence.*

РАЗВИТИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ДИРЕКТОРОВ ШКОЛ СИСТЕМЫ ОБЩЕГО СРЕДНЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *Научная статья предусматривает комплексное развитие культуры общения и социально-психологической профессиональной компетентности директоров школ в процессе управления на основе современных подходов.*

Ключевые слова: *общее образование, школа, управление, социально-психологическая, компетентность.*

Relevance of the topic: If we look at the history of human development, the development of any country or society has been directly dependent on the attention paid to the education system and quality personnel management. As a result of relying on such methodological connections, the management process has achieved an active rise in socio-psychological aspects. In addition to the fundamental reform of the general secondary education system, which is the foundation of the personnel training system, special attention is being paid to improving the social and psychological competence of school principals. Also, material support for principals of general secondary schools, systematic improvement of their qualifications, proper organization of pedagogical activities of general education school staff, further increasing the status and prestige of pedagogical staff in society, many laws and programs have been developed in order to improve the lifestyle of teachers and mentors, create the necessary conditions for their conscious activity and free creativity, and effective work is being carried out in this regard.

We can see that the rational policy and all consistent reforms in our country are based on serious attention to education and modern requirements for high-quality personnel. At this point, it should be noted that in order to further develop the public education system, increase the quality and efficiency of education, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Additional measures to reform the public education system The implementation of Decree No.22 dated February 3, 2022, requires creative approaches from many leaders and pedagogues working in the public education system. On May 12 of this year, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev issued a decree "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" and "On additional measures for the development of public education" " signed the decision.

The purpose of the research is to further develop the culture of communication of school principals on the basis of national values and to build their socio-psychological professional competence by modernizing the activities of school principals, to address problems and shortcomings in the management process.

The main objectives of the study: to increase the personal responsibility and accountability of leaders of the general education system, the introduction of incentives that have a positive impact on the effectiveness of the educational process, the involvement of modern innovative technologies in the educational process, broad-minded high competence formation of a reserve of leaders, training of leading personnel for the improvement of education and science of the country, raising the prestige and discipline of teachers in our society, regular training of active and dedicated teachers in the community to strengthen, to treat students with respect to teachers, to educate students in the spirit of creativity, to create opportunities for young people interested in scientific and creative activities in the general education system, to work in a team. Forming an environment of mutual respect, team building knowledge, skills, competencies and professional skills y Ensuring regular increase, taking into account the specifics of the soup, expanding the participation of the private sector in the education system.

Based on the above objectives, the objectives of the study were identified:

- a) adapting the culture of communication to modern requirements through the formation of socio-psychological professional competence in school principals;
- b) the formation of social relations, social consciousness, social outlook and modern image through the formation of new relationships in the minds of school principals;
- c) develop a creative adaptation and a serious approach to their work;
- g) training in the application of non-standard solutions and development techniques in order to be effective;
- d) directing the use of effective control methods to regulate community activities;
- e) be able to use improved options for keeping distance between teacher and students, and b.

Based on the above, it should be noted that the development of a culture of communication and socio-psychological professional competence of the leaders of the general education system is the basis for the modernization of their activities. Because the interests of the state and society are achieved through the correct and effective management of the education sector by competent leaders.

This begs the question. What is a communication process? In what sense is behavior used? What is morality? What does the concept of professional competence mean? What is the meaning of the word profession?

At the heart of the research topic, every management process seems easy at first glance. In fact, the management process in the system of social relations requires from the manager a serious and complex professional-psychological approach, the ability to communicate correctly and appropriately, a high level of competence. Therefore, the above questions are covered in terms of content and substance.

Communication is an Arabic word meaning "to see, meet, receive." That is why communication is a human process. In the process of different activities, people want to say something to each other. Communication is a multifaceted process of developing connections between people based on the need for interaction. Communication involves the exchange of information between co-workers.

In the textbook "Social Psychology" V.M.Karimova, one of the leading scientists in the field of psychology in our country, talks about communication, which is a necessity for the management process and the basis of social relations. "One of the most important tasks of

communication is its participation in social behavior and its coordination. Because the direct purpose and essence of social behavior is to influence people, scientists are focusing on its direction and importance in society. ” At the same time, when it comes to the above-mentioned forms of social behavior, among them the forms of behavior that determine the place of the individual in society, his prestige and destiny among people are becoming increasingly important. For example:

- qualities that show kindness and kindness, friendship or enmity between people;
- Factors to achieve a specific goal or to secure power;
- Behavior of the person in cases of self-confidence (assertiveness) or depression (helplessness).

Among the social forms of human behavior associated with kindness and compassion, altruism, that is, the tendency to give generously to others, is becoming one of the most important values of our century.

Research has shown that the process of interpersonal communication, which at first glance may seem easy in human society, is in fact very complex, determined by the acquisition of skills, abilities and experiences necessary for a person to learn and live throughout his life.

Scientific research and analytical studies show that in the management of a modern education system, communication is psychologically important in the system of interactions, how complex it is and is a key tool for the exchange of information. "Communication is such a multifaceted phenomenon and process in the system of social relations that I recommend to include the following at the same time:

- 1) the process of positive or negative interpersonal interaction;
- 2) the process of exchanging information and data between people;
- 3) the process by which individuals interact with each other;
- 4) the process of influencing one's self and others;
- 5) the process by which individuals feel and understand each other (empathy);
- 6) the process of influencing the professional relationship between managers and pedagogical staff

In the process of governance, communication is seen as the main means of influencing all aspects of the relationship, as well as revealing the true nature of social life.

In the process of moral management, a person is able to behave in difficult situations, to be civilized, to be polite when giving tasks to subordinates, to be considerate of subordinates, to reward their success in a timely manner. finds the expression z.

As we highlight the concepts of competence and professionalism required for the management process, they are interpreted as follows.

"**Competence**" is used in the sense of effective use of theoretical knowledge in practice, the ability to demonstrate a high level of professionalism, skills, abilities and talents. To date, many types of competencies have been researched by domestic and foreign scientists and researchers.

In short, almost all social qualities of a person are formed and developed under the influence of the external social environment. Therefore, goal-oriented education and upbringing, as well as the free choice of the pupil, play a leading role in the formation of human qualities.

In order to further develop the activities of the general education system, the following main directions of modern requirements have been identified for the leaders:

□ as a modern leader to be committed to national values, to be able to effectively organize their activities, to have new approaches to governance;

□ to be an entrepreneur who participates in the development of the country with new ideas, to show himself as a leader who is able to come to the forefront in time and put into practice new methods;

□ Training of a new generation of personnel with high intellectual and spiritual potential with socio-psychological professional competence, the formation of the necessary knowledge, skills and competencies for graduates of educational institutions to become modern professionals.

In general, improving the performance of the leaders of the general education system is tantamount to ensuring the development of the country, while achieving quality education for students will further enhance the future of the nation.

REFERENCES

1. V.M.Karimova. "Social Psychology" - T.: "Science and Technology" Publishing House, 2017, 58-59 pages.
2. David G. Mayers Psychology, © 2010 by Worth Publishers. 590-p.
3. Kelvin Seifert and Rosemary Sutton, Educational Psychology © 2019, Second Edition. 324-p.
4. Ismailovich A. S. PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING PSYCHOLOGY OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE OF UZBEK FAMILY //Scientific reports of Bukhara State University. – 2020. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 313-318.
5. Saidov A. SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FORMATION OF A CULTURE OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN THE FAMILY //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. B7. – C. 867-871.
6. Sharifjon To'lqin o'g A. et al. TA'LIM-TARBIYA TIZIMI VA O'QITUVCHILAR FAOLIYATIDA PSIXOLOGIK XIZMATNING AHAMIYATI //MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 57-60.
7. Azamat, S. (2022). On The Basis Of National Values To Raise A Healthy Generation In The Family. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 6(10), 2417-2420.
8. Ismailovich S. A. Socio-Psychological Problems of Educating an Independent-Minded, Creative Person in the Educational Process //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 4-7.